

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

Sumas Wongsunopparat¹, Ohnmar Haelin Rai²

¹PhD, Johnson Graduate School of Management, Cornell University, United States of America MBA, Tepper School of Business, Carnegie Mellon University, United States of America

²Master of Business Administration Bangkok University, Bangkok, Thailand

ABSTRACT: The study compares foreign and local brands, focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni, and local brands, in order to uncover the elements that impact customers' brand choice decisions in Thailand. The study looked at the elements that influence a customer's decision to buy a custom-made suit, in order to figure out what the most important component is. Understanding how Marketing Mix affects customer happiness and purchase decisions is especially important. The second goal is to investigate how brand equity affects sales, with a particular focus on customer brand preferences and market expansion.

The author chose the survey approach for this study, which is a quantitative research. Data was collected at random online through 346 legitimate questionnaires, and data was analyzed using cross tabulation and multinomial logistic regression. The study's findings show that all of the investigated factors, including product, price, location, promotion, brand equity, and customer purchase behavior determinants, have a positive impact on tailoring's customer brand choice decision in Thailand, with some specifications of each factor being found to be significant. Finally, when comparing these three brands, certain results are noteworthy.

KEYWORDS: Tailoring Brands, Customer Brand Choice Decision, 4Ps Marketing Mix, Brand Equity, Customer Purchase Behavior Determinants, Customer Lifestyle

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

When come to the fashion, it is existed in the earliest century of mankind. At that time, fashion was associated with the aspect of beauty and concerned the expression of physical power through body adornment. The late 19th and early 20th centuries saw the emergence of an addition to male costume, namely the men's suit. It was, like many of its predecessors, an ensemble of jacket, waistcoat and trousers. What made this newcomer special, however, was that all three pieces were made of the same or similar fabric and it had no waist seam, allowing for mass production. Upon its arrival, few imagined the wide recognition this men's costume would enjoy today, as "perhaps the most successful and enduring fashion garment ever invented," replacing most of its predecessors. Tailoring is the art of designing, cutting, fitting, and finishing clothing. The word tailor comes from the French tailor, to cut, and appears in English in the fourteenth century. In Latin, the word for tailor was "sartor," meaning "mending" or "mending," hence the English term "sartorial," which refers to the tailor, tailoring, or bespoke clothing. The term "Bespoke" or "Custom Tailoring" describes garments that are made to measure for a specific customer. Bespoke tailoring signals that these garments are already "taken" and not made on spec. As a craft, tailoring dates back to the early Middle Ages when tailors' guilds were established in major European cities. The beginnings of tailoring can be traced back to the craft of linen armor smiths, who fitted men with padded linen undergarments to protect their bodies from the chafing of chainmail and later plate armor. Men's clothing at this time consisted of loose-fitting tunic and trousers.

What is the different between ready-made suit and Custom-made suit?

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

The advantage of custom-made suits is that you may choose the materials used in the manufacturing process as well as the style of the garment. Furthermore, choosing a tailored suit means being able to customize the majority of the suit's features and details, such as fabric, pockets, buttons, single or double breasted, jacket lining and lapels, trouser length and pleats, internal embroidery, and many other details that make the suit truly personalized.

Even if ready-to-wear clothing comes in a variety of models and styles, it is virtually always essential to alter it, at least in terms of the length of the sleeves and pants. As a result, we must constantly keep in mind that the cost of any ready-made suit will include an additional charge for various changes. Because they are fitted to the precise anatomical measurements, made-to-measure clothes fit better than ready-made outfits. The beginning price is comparable to ready-to-wear suits, but depending on the quality of the chosen materials and the level of customization, they can be more expensive.

Ermenegildo Zegna

Ermenegildo Zegna founded its company in 1910 in the Northern Italian town of Trivero with the dream of creating the most beautiful fabrics in the world. Since then it has become one of Italy's best known dynamic family businesses. The company is now run by the third generation, with Gildo as CEO, Paolo as Chairman and Anna as President of Fondazione Zegna. He sourced the highest quality natural fibres directly from their country of origin, imported them to Italy to be expertly woven, and then exported these luxury fabrics while making the Zegna brand known worldwide. Ermenegildo Zegna's legacy, opened its first boutique in Paris in 1980, followed by stores in London and Milan. When the company opened its Beijing boutique in 1991, it became the first luxury menswear brand in China, continuing the entrepreneurial spirit of its founder. Today, Ermenegildo Zegna is the world leader in luxury menswear with a retail network that includes more than 500 stores in over 100 countries around the world. Zegna upholds the founder's heritage by following three principles: defining long-term goals, keeping family ownership to assure continuity, and adhering to a sound ethical commitment codified in a rigorous corporate governance framework.

Brioni

In 1985, Brioni became the first Italian tailoring company to open a school to train new tailors. The four-year school, named after one of the brand's two founders Nazareno Fonticoli Scuolo Superiore di Sartoria, is located at the Brioni factory in Penne and takes students step-by-step through the 220 manufacturing processes required to make a typical Brioni suit. Brioni is perhaps the best known bespoke menswear brand in the world, and for good reason. The Italian clothing manufacturer practically invented the term "power suit" with its broad-shouldered, broad-chested suit style. The suits, made at the company's factory in Penne in southern Abruzzo, are mostly handmade and include as many as 33 proprietary details, from cashmere under the collar (optional) to double-stitched buttonholes and inside lapels not found on a typical bespoke men's suit. True to its motto "to be one of a kind," Brioni continually raises the bar when it comes to offering exclusive fabrics and bespoke services that few other luxury brands can match. The brand is also a big proponent of the three-piece suit, now crafted in cashmere, worsted Vicuna and fine micron wool, many with overlapping micro and macro patterns.

Local brand

Thailand has hundreds of tailors offering their services, and signs all over the city advertising men's suits tailored in 24 hours for 4,000 baht and promoters trying to lure tourists into shops with the promise of cheap bespoke clothing. Sure, it's tempting to get something as cheap as possible, but when you're in the market for tailored clothing, remember that you get what you pay for. You're already saving significantly compared to what you'd pay at home; it's foolish to get a bargain if you risk being unsatisfied. While the cheaper tailors are often very skilled, the cost savings are usually offset by the quality of the material. The selection at the cheaper stores is usually limited to synthetic blends with little, if any, wool and other natural materials. At your first fitting, you pick out the fabrics and the tailor takes all your measurements. If you're not already, you'll be well versed in terms like "flat front," "spread collar," "slim cut," and "notch" as you'll be picking out all the specifications of your suit and shirt. If this is all too confusing, most good tailors can advise you and tell you what looks best on your body, or you can even bring your favorite suit to the consultation.

When you come in for your second fitting, the garment won't be ready yet, but you'll be trying on the rough pieces to check the fit. If you're really in a hurry, or the garment fits perfectly at the second fitting, the tailor is done. But it's always better to try everything on one last time.

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

1.2 Research objective

As well, these three brands are located in the around Thailand with the different price and quality. Although, each brand is still able to lead on their potential client who is the first time to visit their store and repeating Customers. Therefore the object of this research is

1. To find out factors that effect on customer's brand choice decision between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni And Local brand.
2. To understand Thai cultural of the international brand and local brand.
3. To understand how the customers are effected on marketing mix 4ps, quality, customer behavior in customer's choice of the brand.

1.3 Purpose of study

1. To find out the factor influencing customer choice in buying custom suit of Global and local brand in Thailand.
2. To find out the factors influencing the brand choice decision of tailoring consumers in order to understand what is the most important factor influencing customers' decisions. Specifically, understanding how Marketing Mixed affects customer satisfaction and purchase decision.

1.4 Scope of study

The research is concern with the customer brand choice by focusing on marketing mix(4Ps), brand and buying behavior will be use in this independent study. The researcher used questionnaires as an instrument to survey to collect data and define scope of this study as follow:

1.4.1 Scope of Content

The researcher clarified this study with research descriptions as focusing factors; brand, product, price, place, Promotion, customer behavior and lifestyle of the customer in Thailand. This research aims to determine the factors that influence Thai customers' brand choice decisions by comparing international and local Tailoring brands in Thailand. The tailoring chains compared are Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni, Local Brand in Thailand. The study applied a quantitative method to collect data through online questionnaires.

1.4.2 Scope of Population

This research included the demographics of Thai customers, ranging in age from under 18 to over 51. The target demographics were collected randomly.

1.4.3 Scope of variable

The study consists of the independent and dependent variables. The independent variables include brand, product, price, place, promotion and customer behavior factors. The dependent variable is Thai customers' brand choice comparing Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand in Thailand.

1.5 Limitation of study

Research has a limitation as time, since the data collection of this study is via online questionnaires only. Therefore, the results of this study cannot be generalized to other tailoring businesses and cannot be generalized to other brands besides comparing Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand. However, this study provides useful information for tailoring marketers to improve their business, products or services, and can also use the data to predict customers' brand choice behavior.

1.6 Research question

Since the research topic is what influences Thai customers' choice of custom made suit, a comparison between international and local brand chains is conducted with focus on comparing Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni, Local Brand in Thailand. Therefore, the research questions are developed based on the research objective, which are designed as follows:

- ✓ What factors that influence on customer's brand choice decision towards tailoring focusing on top three brands: Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni, Local Brand in Thailand.
- ✓ Do brand, marketing mix of the 4Ps and customer behavior influence customers' brand choice decisions between international (Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni) and local (Local Brand) tailoring brands in Thailand?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter of the literature review examines how customers choose their merchandise and it relates to their decision and perception regarding the clothing of the merchandise and the outcome as making a brand choice decision. In order to understand the behavior, perception and lifestyle of customers in relation to marketing, it is necessary to study these factors by

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

learning with Literature Review. In addition, the study of brand equity is another area that can also help in understanding customer decision making. The purpose of this study is to investigate customer perception and preference towards Tailor made suit focusing on brands Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni, Local Brand. The study aims to focus on the factors that influence customer choice of custom made suit in Thailand along with the relationship of demographic variables. The research mentioned the following factors for this chapter with details;

- Marketing Mix (4Ps)
- Brand equity
- Customer behavior
- Customer life's style
- Choice theory
- Hypothesis
- Theoretical Framework

2.1 Marketing Mix (4Ps)

2.1.1 Product

A product is a thing or service that an industry produces in big quantities in a set number of units. It is possible for a product to be both tangible and intangible. All of the products must match customer demand. Knowing the problem or putting the feature of products or service and unique point of product for consumers is the key to a successful product.

H1o: Product does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H1a: Product does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

2.1.2 Price

Pricing has always been an important part of marketing, only pricing generates money among the traditional marketing aspects. One of the most basic, yet crucial issues facing a firm is what price to charge customers for products and services. Price setting is essentially seen as an optimization problem: setting a price too high can have the impact of indirectly reducing profits through a drop-in market share, while setting a price too low might have the impact of directly reducing earnings through a low profit margin. The most essential premise of marketing, according to Haxthausen (2008), is to fulfill and surpass client needs. One of the customer's expectations is to get a high-quality product at a low cost. Companies must try to deliver items that match all client criteria while being offered at a lower price than equivalent items from competitors, depending on the product and the market.

H2o: Price does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H2a: Price does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

2.1.3 Place

The distribution channel is commonly referred to as "place". Any physical or virtual store can be used as a location. Physical distribution refers to the process of moving things from the manufacturer to the customer. If the product is a business product, a business team will be necessary to communicate with various clients and ensure that the product is available to them. Because distribution has such a large impact on profitability, a company's supply chain and logistics management plan should be effective.

H3o: Place does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H3a: Place does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

2.1.4 promotion

One of the most powerful factors in the marketing mix is promotion. Publicity, public relations, exhibitions, and demonstrations are examples of sales promotion activities. The degree of marketing expenditure on promotion is determined by the marketing manager. When communication raises awareness, it piques clients' curiosity, prompting them to make a purchase decision.

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

Different communication methods might be utilized for promotion. Advertising specialties, cash refund offers/rebates, contests and sweepstakes, coupons, patronage awards, point-of-purchase displays, premiums, price packs/cents-off bargains, samples, and trade fairs are all used by businesses to enhance sales.

H4o: Promotion does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H4a: Promotion does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

2.2 Brand equity

There are three steps to managing brand equity. The first step is to introduce yourself. Begin with a high-quality product, then develop a brand image that generates favorable consumer feedback. Elaboration is the next step. At this stage, the goal should be to instill attitude accessibility in the consumer's mind and make the brand easy to recall. The next goal is to boost brand equity by encouraging consumers to engage in direct behavioral experiences and express their attitudes as often as feasible. Fortification is the final stage. The goal is to increase the value of one's brand by extending it to other products. Perceptual fit, competitive leverage, and benefit transfer are all required for successful brand extensions. According to (Aaker 1991), The value that people identify with a brand is known as brand equity. When compared to other brands, it is the consumers' sense of the overall superiority of a product bearing that brand name. Rather than any objective indications, brand equity pertains to the perception of customers (Lassar et al.1995). "The set of associations and behaviors on the part of the brand's consumers, channel members, and parent corporation that allows the brand to earn greater volume or higher margins than it would otherwise earn the brand name and that gives the brand a strong, sustainable, and differentiated advantage over competitors," according to Lance Leuthesser. This definition acknowledges the existence of brand equity as a concept but does not go into detail on the characteristics of brands.

2.2.1 Brand Loyalty

Consumers who are devoted to a brand may be willing to pay extra for it because they believe it offers them something that no other brand can. Brand loyalty leads to greater market share when the same brand is repeatedly purchased by loyal consumers, irrespective of situational constraints. Various studies have acknowledged the importance of consumer brand loyalty to a brand's success and continued expansion. Through word of mouth, existing committed customers introduce the brand to new customers. Customers that are loyal to the company are regarded as extremely important because they provide consistent revenue that might last for a long period. As a result, one of a business entity's key goals is to retain and keep its customers loyal in order to maximize and benefit from client lifetime value. Loyal consumers' switching rates will be reduced, resulting in a higher value for them. As a result, client loyalty is a key component of a company's long-term financial performance. According to Oliver (1999) "Brand loyalty is a deeply held commitment to re buy or re patronize a preferred brand consistently in the future, thereby causing repetitive same brand or same brand set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behavior". Dick and Basu (1994) looked at different levels of consumer loyalty, claiming that a better indicator of repeat purchases may be found by comparing it to other competitors. They discovered four types of loyalty as a result of this combination.

1. True Loyalty- True loyalty can be achieved by combining a positive attitude with a high level of patronage from the same provider. This is the ideal scenario for any company or service provider that wants to build a loyal consumer base.
2. Latent loyalty - When the number of repeat purchases at the same provider is limited or none at all, but the favorable attitude is significant, this is referred to as latent loyalty.
3. Spurious loyalty - Spurious loyalty occurs when there is no or a weak relative attitude but a high degree of recurring purchases, indicating that there is behavioral but not attitudinal loyalty.
4. No loyalty - No loyalty is a mix of a negative attitude and a lack of purchasing power.

J.M.M. Bloemer, H.D.P. Kasper (1995) defined as True brand loyalty is: (1) a biased (i.e. non-random), (2) behavioral response (i.e. purchase), (3) expressed over time, (4) by some decision-making unit, (5) with respect to one or more alternative brands out of a set of such brands, and (6) is a function of psychological (decision making, evaluative) processes resulting in brand commitment.

2.2.2 Brand Awareness

Brand awareness refers to the likelihood that customers are aware of the product's lifespan and availability. It also gives the brand a competitive advantage. Furthermore, consumer views of pricing fairness are likely to be influenced by brand

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

recognition. When a customer is aware of a product's popularity, that brand awareness aids the focal price in competing favorably with alternative prices or the internal reference price.

Customer loyalty is linked to the functions of brand identities in customers' memories, and it may be measured by how effectively they can recognize the brand under different circumstances. Consumers' brand awareness relates to their ability to recall or recognize a brand, or simply if they are aware of it. In general, brand awareness is a broad and nebulous phrase that is intuitively recognized by employees in most businesses. It may be characterized as a tool that focuses on defining and generating a target audience's familiarity and recognizability with a specific brand. Consumer awareness is a tool that businesses employ to influence consumer attitudes toward a brand or company by developing associations and beliefs among a target audience about a company or product.

2.2.3 Brand Familiarity

Brand familiarity is a term that refers to the amount of time a firm has spent developing brand information by interacting with the content of the processing. Another meaning of brand familiarity is a one-dimensional concept that is proportional to the amount of time spent processing information about the brand, independent of the nature or substance of the information processing. As a result, brand familiarity is the most basic level of consumer understanding.

Brand familiarity, according to Baker et al. (1986), is a one-dimensional concept that is proportional to the amount of time spent processing information about the brand, regardless of the nature or substance of the processing. Familiarity appears to be a catch-all term that is related to other relevant categories such as consumer expertise, prior knowledge, and belief strength, though not perfectly. Familiarity appears to be a required, but not sufficient, condition for the development of competence and the ability to successfully perform product-related tasks. It is critical to establish a positive brand association and brand belief in order to determine the success of a consumer's attitude toward a brand or company.

2.2.4 Brand Reputation

Brand reputation is becoming increasingly essential, according to both academics and practitioners. Brands must have a positive reputation in order to be successful and so profitable. One of the most important factors in determining the perceived quality of a brand's products is its reputation. Because the brand adds credibility, consumers anticipate things manufactured today to be of comparable quality to products manufactured previously. Brand reputation is more than just keeping customers happy; it is something a firm earns through time and refers to how different audiences perceive the brand. Companies and brands with a favorable reputation are more likely to attract customers, while brands that continually fail to meet their stated aims or marketing signals will lose their positive reputation—and eventually develop a negative reputation. According to Dowling (2001), a brand's or company's reputation is made up of a mix of trustworthiness, adoration, compassion, respect, and confidence in the organization's current and likely future activities — a mix that can easily be squandered. Brand reliability is helping to advance our understanding of what variables weaken or strengthen a brand, as well as the limits of brand extendibility and the need of establishing a brand portfolio.

2.2.5 Brand perceived Quality

Customers' opinions of product or service quality or superiority are referred to as brand perceived quality. It is solely dependent on the customer's assessment of the product's capacity to meet their expectations. According to this, brand perceived quality stems from recent brand experiences that customers have had with products or services, influencing their decision to purchase such products or services. Furthermore, brand quality encompasses both brand recognition and customer perceptions of the brand. There are two types of elements that influence perceived quality: intrinsic and external qualities. Extrinsic qualities include price, brand name, store, packaging, and production information, among other things. Intrinsic attributes are tied to the physical pieces of a product, whereas extrinsic attributes are not. Perceived quality differs from objective quality in that it is the customer's assessment of a product's overall excellence or superiority.

H5o: Brand does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H5a: Brand does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

2.3 Customer's Brand choice decision

Almost all microeconomic analysis is based on individual decision-making. The conventional economic model of rational decision-making is outlined in these notes. There is a formation of competitive advantage that influences customer decision based on branding and brand-related differentiation. Many studies looked into how customers distinguish and value brands by looking into brand equity, brand personality, and brand extensions. Furthermore, researchers have discovered that customers

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

differ not only in their perceptions of brands, but also in their relationships with them (Fournier, 1998; Muniz and O Guinn, 2001).

2.3.1 Consumer's behavior

The customer and the interaction between the company and the customer are central to the marketing philosophy and process. If this is characterized by skepticism and distrust, businesses are unlikely to be able to persuade customers to make the changes necessary to achieve sustainability. Customer behavior is the study of how customers, whether individuals, groups, or organizations, acquire, utilize, and give ideas, commodities, and services to meet their requirements. It relates to a customer's action and determining their purpose for that action. Consumer behavior combines components from psychology, sociology, social anthropology, marketing, and economics, according to Lynn R. Kahle and Angeline G. Close's study. It aids businesspeople in comprehending buyer decision-making processes, both individually and collectively, as well as how emotions influence purchase behavior. It investigates individual consumer factors such as demographics and behavioral aspects in order to better understand client needs.

2.3.2 Consumer's perception

The term "consumer perception" refers to a sensory paradigm of marketing and advertising. It depicts how customers view and process firms or products through five senses until they reach the final degree of purchasing decision. Furthermore, customers' perceptions are influenced by three factors: self-perception, price perception, and benefit perception.

2.3.3 Consumer's purchasing decision

Consumers will have chosen which characteristics are vital for meeting their demands by the time they reach this stage, which is also important. Consumers will have already decided what they want to buy, which can be based on previous experience or advertisements. The marketer must have gone to great lengths to make sure his product is perfect (Frain, 1996). The customer purchase decision-making process, according to Engel, Blackwell, and Miniard (1995), can be divided into five steps: problem detection, information search, alternative evaluation, buy choice, and post-purchase behavior.

H6o: Consumer Behavior does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H6a: Consumer Behavior does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

2.4 Customer's lifestyle

For marketing purposes, a fashion lifestyle aims to reflect the ideals and inspiration of a group or culture. Based on their decisions, experiences, and backgrounds such as social class, nationality, and race, each individual has their own style or identity. According to this fashion lifestyle, the goal is to sell things by sending customers a message that their identity will be supported by the public and the company. People are divided into divisions depending on what they want to do and how they spend their discretionary income, according to the lifestyle marketing concept. Consumers frequently favor certain items, services, and activities over others because they are associated with a particular way of life. As a result, lifestyle-marketing methods aim to position a product by integrating it into an existing consumption pattern.

2.5 Choice Theory

One of the fundamental parts of marketing science is brand choice theory. Almost all marketing decisions contain assumptions – explicit or implicit – about how customers make purchasing decisions and how strategic marketing variables (such as price, advertising, and distribution) influence these decisions. According to Kippax and Crawford (1993), choice theory is based on the notion that all behaviors express an individual's intention to meet their five basic needs in their current situation. And no behavior is the result of an event or a person other than the individual. The utility-maximization approach to choose has several properties that help to explain why it has dominated economic analysis for so long. First and foremost, it has been strongly rooted in the ideals of government policymaking since its inception. Second, empirical studies tend to corroborate many of the choice theory's comparative statics prophesy - the qualitative prophecy about how people's choices change as their environments change. Third, the optimization approach (including utility maximization and profit maximization) has an extremely wide scope. Fourth, the optimization approach provides a compact theory that makes experiential predictions from a relatively scanty model of the choice problem. (Levin & Milgrom, 2004). All behavior, according to Choose Theory, describes an individual's regular endeavor to meet one or more basic natural needs. Accepting this concept requires persons who believe in the stimulus–response theory to set an example. According to this stimulus-response model, someone or something outside the person causes behavior, and the action that follows is a response to that stimulus. People always have authority over the action

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

part of behavior, according to the Choice theory, and if they change that element, they cannot avoid affecting the cognitive, feeling, and physiological components as well. People must know that they always have control over the doing component and can choose to do something more important than being dejected in order to get their needs addressed effectively.

2.7 Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

4. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The purpose of this chapter is to show and analyze the results collected from the SPSS data, as well as to provide answers to the research questions. The author will provide the results of a total of 346 respondents who completed the survey form entirely. Further, this chapter presents the results of the data collection which is based upon the result methodology discussed in Chapter 3.

4.1 The analysis of multinomial logistic regression method to explain the significant of general information (7 Likert scale)

The researcher will use multinomial logistic regression to examine data in this section. Multinomial logistic regression is a classification approach that generalizes logistic regression to multiclass issues, i.e. situations with more than two distinct discrete outcomes, as discussed. Given a set of independent variables, it's a model for predicting the probabilities of several

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

possible outcomes of a categorically distributed dependent variable (which may be real-valued, binary-valued, categorical-valued, etc.).

Because the dependent variable in this study is nominal or equivalently categorical, meaning that it falls into any one of a set of categories that cannot be arranged in any meaningful way and for which there are more than two categories, multinomial logistic regression is used.

Table 4.1: Hypothesis test: Model Fitting Information

Model Fitting Information				
Model	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null	638.050			
Final	491.479	146.570	88	.000

Table 4.2: Hypothesis test: Likelihood Ratio Tests

Likelihood Ratio Tests				
Effect	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Brand	520.272	28.792	14	.011
Product	547.279	55.800	16	.000
Price	501.785 ^a	10.306	14	.739
Place	509.695 ^a	18.215	14	.197
Promotion	523.253	31.774	14	.004
BuyerBehavior	513.631 ^a	22.152	14	.076

From table 4.2, there are 6 factors analyzed in this part:

Dependent variable

Consumer brand choice of Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

Independent variable

H1 Brand

H2 Product

H3 Price

H4 Promotion

H5 Place

H6 Buyer Behavior

From Multinomial Logistic Regression, it shows that those variables whose p-value < .05 (in red), all significantly influence consumer choice in purchasing vehicle. Therefore, we can reject the following null hypotheses (Ho):

H1o: Brand does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H2o: Product does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H3o: Price does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H4o: Promotion does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

local brands in Thailand.

H5o: Place does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H6o: Consumer Behavior does not affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

And accept the following alternative hypotheses (H_a):

H1a: Brand does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H2a: Product does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H3a: Price does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H4a: Promotion does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H5a: Place does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

H6a: Consumer Behavior does affect customers' brand choice decisions comparing between Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and local brands in Thailand.

5. DISCUSSION

In this chapter, the researcher presents the most relevant aspects of this study, as well as a discussion of the study's findings and recommendations for future research. The major goal of the research is to look at the elements that influence consumer brand choices of tailoring suits in Thailand, specifically Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni, and local brands. The study was conducted in Thailand from the 15th of January to the 1st of March 2021 for the benefit of business owners, investors, and marketing specialists interested in Thai custom suit consumers.

5.1 Conclusion

5.1.1 Brand Factor

The majority of Tailor made suit shoppers base their choice to buy a tailor item on brand awareness. As we all know, most tailor firms engage with their customers through a variety of methods, but not all of them succeed in attracting client attention and making them aware of their brand. As a result, tailor brands should strengthen their methods for raising awareness among their target or potential clients. If this campaign is successful, it will help the brand stay top of mind with clients, and they will be more likely to return to the same store whenever they need fast fashion.

5.1.2. Product factor

Most tailoring suit clients are aware that most suit brands sell identical items in terms of patterns, fabrics, and stitching quality. As a result, the tailoring industry should consider this to be a weak spot in its business and work to improve it in order to get more sales from the suit market.

5.1.3. Price factor

Customers prefer to buy merchandises at competitive prices in the market, including cheaper prices than other brands with good quality, according to research. As a result, it is critical for the tailoring sector to be aware of and attempt to balance their merchandise's price in order to best satisfy customer expectations.

5.1.4 Promotion factor

Even if there is a large discount, most suit purchasers pay attention to Celebration advertising and season promotions from each brand. The reason for this may be that they want to see what kind of design is used, as well as how the suit fits and looks on the celebrity. Another example is when it comes to wedding season, consumers begin to shop for suits because there will be more fabric and design available. As a result, it is critical for the tailoring sector to be aware of and attempt to balance their merchandise's promotion in order to best satisfy customer expectations.

5.1.5 Place Factor

The majority of Thai tailor suit customers are unconcerned with online ordering. They value a stand-alone business since they can choose their preferred fabric and material for the suit at their leisure. Another reason is that they personally measure your size in their single store.

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

Why using Multinomial Logistic Regression?

5.2 Multinomial Logistic Regression

When the dependent variable is nominal with more than two levels, multinomial logistic regression is the linear regression analysis to employ. Multinomial Logistic Regression is a type of logistic regression that allows researchers to categorize participants based on the values of a set of predictor variables. It is similar to logistic regression, but it is more straightforward because the dependent variable is not limited to two categories. The researcher can estimate the level of influence of a person's age, gender, and dating status on genre of favored movies using a Multinomial Logistic Regression. As a result, the researcher can target a certain advertising campaign to the people who are most likely to view it. The main concept behind logit is to use a logarithmic function to limit the probability value to a certain range (0,1). This is the log odds (the logarithmic of the odds of $y=1$) in technical terms.

In multinomial regression, a probit model is sometimes used instead of a logit model. The graph below depicts the differences between a logit and a probit model for various values (-4,4). In ordinal regression, both models are typically employed as the link function.

Finger 2; Differences Between Logit and Probit Multinomial Regression Models

However, the logit function is used in the majority of multinomial regression models. Because probit assumes a normal distribution of the probability of the occurrence, but logit assumes a log distribution, the difference between the two functions is often only visible in small samples.

5.3 Recommendation for Future Research

Marketing mix, tailor suit attitude about brand equity, culture variables, and personal elements that influence customer decision toward tailoring brand are among the study's research analysis findings. Even though this study provided useful information for tailoring suit marketing strategy, there are many other areas that need to be investigated further, such as customer expectations toward merchandises, the impact of social factors on customer behavior, and additional opportunities for custom made suit in order to expand and develop businesses. The findings of this study can be used to generate standards, guidelines, and development for future tailoring Suits or related fields. This report was only limited to Thailand, thus future research should include a comparative analysis with other country, as well as more demographic factors for future studies. Furthermore, having a solid understanding of technology and marketing can assist corporations or companies in developing a good business strategy.

REFERENCES

- 1) Alison Matthews David ,14 May 2021 " Tailoring" ;
<<https://fashion-history.lovetoknow.com/fashion-clothing-industry/tailoring>>

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

- 2) ROBB REPORT STAFF; Jul 11, 2553 BE "Brioni Tailored Clothing"
< <https://robbreport.com/style/fashion/brioni-tailored-clothing-225651/> >
- 3) Home Page of Ermenegildo Zegna <<https://www.zegna.com/th-en/>>
- 4) Suzanne Nam; 4 May 2021 "Tailor-Made: Custom Suits and Clothing in Bangkok"
<<https://www.hachettebookgroup.com/travel/trip-ideas/tailor-made-custom-suits-and-clothing-in-bangkok/>>
- 5) Johan Alfredsson, Lina Augustsson" 2017.15.05– A FORECASTING MODEL OF THE MEN'S SUIT" Thesis for Master, 30 ECTS Textile Management "THE NEXT WAVE OF THE SUIT-ERA"
"https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1144629/FULLTEXT01.pdf "
- 6) Phyo Lai Yee Win; 2016 " THE STUDY OF CONSUMER'S BRAND CHOICE DECISION FOR QUICK SERVICE RESTAURANT (QSR) IN YANGON, MYANMAR FOCUSING ON FAST FOOD BRANDS (KFC, PIZZA HUT & SEASONS) "
- 7) Gentleman's café BLOG- 20 July 2018 "Difference between ready-to-wear, made-to-measure and bespoke men's clothing"
- 8) Martin Skitmore & Hedley Smyth 13 Jun 2007 "Pricing construction work: a marketing viewpoint" Pages 619-630 | Received 27 Jul 2006, Accepted 13 Feb 2007, Published online:
- 9) Faruk Ahmeti 6, June 2015 " Factors Affecting Marketing Strategies: Pricing, Channel Structure and Advertising Strategies" : International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management (IJEEM), Vol. III, Issue
- 10) Meera Singh ; 6 (Sep,-Oct. 2012)" Marketing Mix of 4P'S for Competitive Advantage" IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSRJBM) ISSN: 2278-487X Volume 3, Issue, PP 40-45 www.iosrjournals.org
- 11) Youjae Yi and Hoseong Jeon 2003" Effects of Loyalty Programs on Value Perception, Program Loyalty, and Brand Loyalty" First Published July 1, 2003 Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science; 31; 229
- 12) E Tabaku, M Zerellari –, 2015 "BRAND LOYALTY AND LOYALTY PROGRAMS; A LITERATURE REVIEW" Romanian Economic and Business Review – Vol. 10, No. 2- rebe.rau.ro
- 13) Oliver, Richard. 1999. "Whence customer loyalty?" Journal of Marketing, 63,: 33-44.
- 14) Dick, Alan. S. and Basu, Kunal. 1994. "Customer loyalty: toward an integrated conceptual framework". Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, 22: 99–113.
- 15) Jose M.M. Bloemer- Hans D.P. Kasper "The complex relationship between consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty" Journal of Economic Psychology Volume 16, Issue 2, July 1995, Pages 311-329
- 16) Shirin, Artyom; Puth, Gustav. 2011-11-30 "Customer satisfaction, brand trust and variety seeking as determinants of brand loyalty"
- 17) Emine Sarigöllü 31 January 2014 " How Brand Awareness Relates to Market Outcome, Brand Equity, and the Marketing Mix"
- 18) Hong-Youl Ha, Helen Perks, 02 December 200 " Effects of consumer perceptions of brand experience on the web: brand familiarity, satisfaction and brand trust " Academic Paper
- 19) William Baker, J. Wesley Hutchinson, Danny Moore, and Prakash Nedungadi (1986) ,"Brand Familiarity and Advertising: Effects on the Evoked Set and Brand Preference", in NA - Advances in Consumer Research Volume 13, eds. Richard J. Lutz, Provo, UT : Association for Consumer Research, Pages: 637-642.
- 20) Cleopatra Veloutsou, Luiz Moutinho - "Brand relationships through brand reputation and brand tribalism" Journal of Business Research Volume 62, Issue 3, March 2009, Pages 314-322
- 21) Cleopatra Veloutsou, Luiz Moutinho "Brand relationships through brand reputation and brand tribalism"
- 22) University of Glasgow, Department of Management, The Gilbert Scott Building, Glasgow, G12 8QQ, Scotland, United Kingdom
- 23) Pantea Foroudi "Influence of Brand Signature, Brand Awareness, Brand Attitude, Brand Reputation on Hotel Industry's Brand Performance" International Journal of Hospitality Management Volume 76, Part A, January 2019, Pages 271-285
- 24) Haoqiang Zhu- 2016 "FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMER DOUGHNUT BRAND CHOICE DECISION IN THAILAND, FOCUSING ON MISTER DONUT, DUNKIN' DONUTS AND KRISPY KREME DOUGHNUTS"
- 25) Mariya Kaufman -1989 "Managing brand equity" PH Farquhar - Marketing research, - academia.edu
- 26) Chieng Fayrene Y.L., Goi Chai Lee, "CUSTOMER-BASED BRAND EQUITY: A LITERATURE REVIEW" Researchers World, 2011 - researchgate.net
- 27) Leuthesser, L. (1988). Defining, measuring and managing brand equity: A Conference Summary. (pp. Pages 88-104). Cambridge: MA: Marketing Science Institute

Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Choice Service Tailoring Shop in Thailand, Focusing on Ermenegildo Zegna, Brioni and Local Brand

- 28) Mr. Mukesh B. Ahirrao¹ , Dr. D. S. Pati “Customer Based Brand Equity: A Review of Literature” - International Journal of Creative Research ..., 2017 - researchgate.net
- 29) Paisit Klomkongthong - 2016 “A STUDY OF CONSUMER CHOICE DECISION IN SHOPPING AT COMMUNITY MALL AMONG K- VILLAGE, J-AVENUE AND RAIN HILL ON SUKHUMVIT ROAD, THAILAND”
- 30) Kippax, S., & Crawford, J. (1993). Flaws in the theory of reasoned action. The theory of reasoned action: Its application to AIDS-preventive behavior, 253-269.
- 31) Catarina Peneda de Oliveira , Bruno Miguel Sousa “Green Marketing as a Positive Driver Toward Business Sustainability” 2020 - igi-global.com
- 32) Engel, J. F., Blackwell, R. D., & Miniard, P. W. (1995). Consumer behavior (8th ed). New York: Dryden Press.
- 33) Levin, J., & Milgrom, P. (2004). Introduction to Choice Theory. Retrieved from <http://web.stanford.edu/~jdlevin/Econ>, 20202.